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Waterborne polyurethane-urea dispersion with chain extension step in homogeneous medium reinforced with cellulose nanocrystals

Arantzazu Santamaria-Echart^a, Isabel Fernandes^b, Lorena Ugarte^a, Filomena Barreiro^b, Aitor Arbelaiz^a, Maria Angeles Corcuera^{a,*}, Arantxa Eceiza^{a,**}

^a *Group 'Materials + Technologies', Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Gipuzkoa, University of the Basque Country, Pza Europa 1, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastian, Spain*

^b *Laboratory of Separation and Reaction Engineering (LSRE), Associate Laboratory LSRE/LCM, Polytechnic Institute of Bragança, Campus of Santa Apolonia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal*

Abstract

Waterborne polyurethane-urea (WBPUU) dispersions have gained attention towards environmentally-friendly synthesis routes. Differing from the conventional WBPUU synthesis route where the diamine chain extension is performed in heterogeneous medium in the surface of the already formed particles, in this case the chain extension was carried out in homogeneous medium, prior to WBPUU nanoparticles formation. Thus, stable WBPUU dispersion with small particle sizes and narrow distribution was synthesized. Furthermore, cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) were isolated for the preparation of eco-friendly nanocomposites just by mixing. Nanocomposites with different CNC contents were prepared and extensively characterized in terms of physicochemical, thermal, thermomechanical and mechanical properties, hydrophilic behavior and morphology.

1. Introduction

The use of polyurethane-ureas family is widely extended due to their versatility for a broad range of applications [1,2]. Polyurethane-ureas are composed by two segments: the soft segment (SS), a macrodiol which generally provides flexibility to the material and the hard segment (HS), formed by the isocyanate and amine type chain extender, conferring stiffness to the system [3]. Conventional polyurethane-ureas result hydrophobic systems which can be dissolved in organic solvents. However, the environmental awareness has promoted the research towards eco-friendly materials [4], such as waterborne systems. In this way, by the incorporation of reactants containing ionizable groups covalently bonded to the polymeric chain [5], water dispersible polyurethane-urea systems can be synthesized. Thereby, by the addition of water, polyurethane-urea chains arrange in nanoparticles structure, resulting in waterborne polyurethane-urea (WBPUU) dispersions. Therefore, WBPUU have gained attention due to the green character of their synthesis route, reducing the generation of volatile organic compounds. Furthermore, considering that WBPUU dispersions results stable over months, become them suitable for their use in a wide variety of applications, such as paintings, textile, coatings, inks, medicine, adhesives... [6–11]. Attending to the polyurethane-urea synthesis process, diamine chain extension step can be carried out either in homogeneous medium, before the water addition step or in heterogeneous medium, after the water addition step, once nanoparticles have been formed. Considering the fast reaction rate of diamine with NCO, the chain extension step is usually performed after the phase inversion [12], in heterogeneous medium. Thus, diamine can react with free NCO in the surface of the formed particles [13]. Nevertheless, the possibility of carrying out the diamine chain extension also in homogeneous medium, previous to the dispersion formation step, favors the formation of more uniform WBPUU nanoparticles, resulting in more stable dispersions, as reported in previous works [14]. This factor is essential for their later use, for example in the preparation of nanocomposites just by mixing. In this way, it is worth noting the advantage of using waterborne

systems, which facilitate the incorporation of hydrophilic water dispersible entities in order to enhance the final properties of the material. Among others, eco-friendly cellulose derived reinforcements have gained attention due to their renewability, availability, low cost, biodegradability and biocompatibility [15]. Cellulose is the most abundant biopolymer which can be obtained from different sources like plants, agroindustrial residues or bacteria [16–18]. It offers the possibility of being used in different forms such as fibers or crystals from the nano to macroscale [19]. In this way, cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) have focused interest in the field of nanocomposites considering their elevated length/diameter (L/D) aspect ratio and unique specific mechanical properties in the nanoscale dimension [20]. Furthermore, the final properties of the obtained CNC can be tailored attending to the origin of the raw material [21] as well as to the isolation process [22]. The use of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) for the isolation process favors the anchoring of sulfate groups in CNC surface, which facilitate their dispersibility in water. This fact becomes CNC suitable nanoreinforcement for their incorporation to waterborne polyurethane-ureas without needing chemical modifications or addition of surfactants [23,24].

Therefore, in this work WBPUU was synthesized with diamine chain extension in homogeneous medium, and CNC were isolated for the preparation of WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites loaded with different CNC contents (from 0.5 to 5 wt%). Nanocomposites films were prepared by casting and characterized from the viewpoint of physicochemical, thermal, mechanical, thermomechanical and hydrophilicity properties as well as morphology. A comprehensive study was carried out focusing on the effect of CNC content in the final properties of nanocomposite films.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The synthesis of waterborne polyurethane-urea was carried out using poly(ϵ -caprolactone) diol (PCL) ($M_w = 2000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), provided by Solvay, as soft segment. Hard segment was composed by isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), provided by Bayer, 1,4-butanediol (BD), supplied by Fluka, and ethylenediamine (EDA) purchased from Panreac as chain extenders. 2,2-Bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid (DMPA), purchased from Fluka, was used as internal emulsifier and in order to neutralize the ionic groups of DMPA, triethylamine (TEA), provided by Fluka, was employed. Prior to their use, PCL, BD and DMPA were dried under vacuum at 60 °C. Dry acetone, purchased from Panreac, was employed as viscosity adjuster and dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL), supplied by Fluka was selected as catalyst. Both were used without further purification. Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) powder, provided by Aldrich, was employed for the isolation of cellulose nanocrystals using sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), supplied by Panreac.

2.2. Synthesis of waterborne polyurethane and polyurethane-ureas

WBPUU was synthesized by two-step polymerization process with a PCL/IPDI/DMPA/BD/EDA molar composition of 0.5/3.6/0.5/2/0.6. In this way, considering PCL as soft segment and IPDI, DMPA, BD and EDA as hard segment, a WBPUU with a high hard segment content (52 wt%) was synthesized following previously reported protocol [14]. The reaction was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in controlled conditions and the reaction progress was verified by dibutylamine back titration method according to ASTM D 2572–97. Briefly, PCL, IPDI and 0.037 wt% of DBTDL were mixed and reacted at 80 °C and allowed to react until the NCO theoretical value was reached. The mixture was cooled to 50 °C and, with the purpose of incorporating the ionic groups neutralized, DMPA and TEA were incorporated dissolved in a small amount of dry acetone. Afterwards, the prepolymer was heated to 80 °C and the diol chain extension with BD was carried out. Then, the system was cooled to 45 °C (controlling the viscosity with dry acetone) and the diamine chain extension was carried out in homogeneous medium. EDA dissolved in 30 mL of dry acetone was added at a flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. Finally, in the phase inversion step, distilled water was added dropwise at 25 °C with a flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹ and after removing acetone in a rotary evaporator (at 40 °C and 350 mbar), WBPUU dispersion with a solids content about 35 wt% was obtained. A schematic representation of the chain extension in homogeneous medium as well as dispersion process is shown in Fig. 1a.

2.3. Isolation of cellulose nanocrystals

CNC were isolated from MCC via acid hydrolysis using H_2SO_4 , removing the amorphous regions of MCC using a previously reported method [25]. Briefly, MCC was mixed with 64 wt% of H_2SO_4 at 45 °C for 30 min. The suspension was diluted with deionized water in order to stop the process, and washed by two successive centrifugation cycles of 20 min at 4500 rpm. Afterwards, the suspension was dialyzed against deionized water obtaining a final CNC suspension with around 0.5 wt% solids content and pH about 5–6. Fig. 1b shows a scheme of CNC isolation process.

2.4. WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites preparation

WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites containing from 0.5 to 5 wt% of CNC were prepared by casting. Previously to the preparation of nanocomposites, CNC suspension (0.5 wt%) was sonicated for 1 h and different volumes were added to 9 mL of the previously synthesized WBPUU. With the purpose of maintaining constant the total volume of the nanocomposite dispersions, the required amount of deionized water was added in each case. The obtained dispersions were sonicated for another 1 h and were casted in Teflon moulds and dried in a climatic chamber under controlled conditions (25 °C and 50% of relative humidity) during 1 week. Then, nanocomposite films were dried in a vacuum oven for 3 further days at 25 °C at 800, 600 and 400 mbar, respectively. Films were stored in a desiccator for 1 week previous their characterization. Nanocomposites containing 0.5, 1, 3 and 5 wt% of CNC were coded as WBPUU-X, where X is referred to CNC content (0.5, 1, 3 and 5, respectively). Furthermore, the matrix was also prepared as a reference in the same conditions, denoted as WBPUU. A scheme of nanocomposites preparation is shown in Fig. 1c.

2.5. Characterization

WBPUU dispersion particle size and distribution was analyzed by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using a BI-200SM goniometer from Brookhaven. A detector (BI-APD) placed in a rotary arm was employed for measuring the intensity of the dispersed light at 90°. It was used a luminous source of He-Ne laser (Mini L-30, wavelength $\lambda = 637$ nm, 400 mW). Samples were prepared diluting small amount of the WBPUU dispersion with ultrapure water and averaging 3 measurements at 25 °C.

The sulfate content anchored to the surface of CNC was determined by conductometric titration, using a Crison EC-Meter GLP 31 conductometer calibrated with 147 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, 1413 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and 12.88 mS cm^{-1} standards. Samples were measured in triplicate at 25 °C using NaOH and HCl 10 mM for the titration. The concentration of sulfate groups was also determined by elemental analysis in a Euro EA3000 Elemental Analyzer of Eurovector. Samples were measured by SCAB.PE.29.PR.10.02 method in solid state.

CNC, WBPUU and nanocomposites characteristic functional groups were analyzed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Spectra were carried out using a Nicolet Nexus spectrometer provided with a MKII Golden Gate accessory (Specac) with diamond crystal at a nominal incidence angle of 45° and ZnSe lens. Spectra were recorded averaging 64 scans with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} , in the range from 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} .

Thermal analysis of WBPUU and nanocomposites was performed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in a Mettler Toledo 822e. It was equipped with a robotic arm and an electric intracooler as refrigerator unit. Between 5 and 10 mg of samples were analyzed under nitrogen atmosphere in aluminum pans, by heating from -70 to 180 °C at a flow rate of 40 °C min^{-1} . In thermograms, glass transition temperature (T_g) was referred to the inflection point of the heat capacity, whereas the melting temperature (T_m) was established as the maximum of endothermic peak considering the area under the peak as the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m).

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of WBPUU synthesis process, b) CNC isolation process scheme and c) nanocomposites preparation scheme.

Mechanical tests in tensile mode were carried out in a MTS insight 10 testing machine using a 250 N load cell and pneumatic grips. Samples (8 mm in length, 2.5 mm in width and 0.4 mm in thickness) were tested at a crosshead speed of 50 mm min⁻¹. Five samples were averaged at room temperature obtaining tensile modulus (E), stress at yield (σ_y), stress at break (σ_b) and strain at break (ϵ_b) values from stress strain curves.

Surface hydrophilicity of WBPUU and nanocomposites was analyzed by static water contact angle (WCA) measurements using a Dataphysics OCA20 equipment. Samples were analyzed dropping 2 μ L

deionized water over films surface at room temperature, averaging 6 measurements for each specimen.

The behavior of WBPUU and nanocomposite films immersed in water was studied by water absorption (WA) measurements. Around 15–20 mg of films with a thickness about 0.4 mm were immersed in water at 25 °C and weighed over time until no considerable weight changes were observed. Thereby, water absorption percentage was determined by means of the equation:

$$WA(\%) = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \cdot 100$$

where W_t and W_0 were the weights at time t and at initial time, respectively.

The morphology of WBPUU and nanocomposites was analyzed by atomic force microscopy (AFM) in tapping mode using a Nanoscope IIIa scanning probe microscope (Multimode™ Digital instruments) with an integrated force generated by cantilever/silicon probes, applying a resonance frequency of about 180 kHz. The cantilever had a tip radius of 5–10 nm and was 125 μm long. Samples were prepared by spin-coating a droplet of the dispersions on glass supports.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Polyurethane-urea and CNC dispersions characterization

Particle size and distribution of WBPUU dispersion analyzed by DLS are shown in Fig. 2. It was observed that particles in the nanometric scale were obtained with a dimension of 153 ± 1 nm. Furthermore analyzing Fig. 2a, it was observed that a narrow distribution was obtained, which promotes the stability of the dispersion, enabling storage for months [26]. Fig. 2b and c shows WBPUU dispersion after the synthesis process and after 6 months of storage, respectively, where it can be observed that the dispersion remained visually stable over time. Regarding the reinforcement, the hydrolysis process with H_2SO_4 promotes the anchoring of some sulfate groups to the CNC surface, which induces to electrostatic repulsion forces between CNC, facilitating their dispersibility in polar solvents. In this way, the sulfate content anchored to the surface of CNC during the hydrolysis process was determined by conductometric titration, resulting in a value of 0.73%. The result was corroborated by elemental analysis, where a sulfur content of 0.70% was obtained. In addition, CNC morphology was analyzed by AFM and height and phase images are shown in Fig. 2d and e, respectively. It was observed that CNC were isolated and presented a rod-like morphology. The length/diameter (L/D) aspect ratio of the CNC was determined by averaging 100 CNC entities. The length of the CNC were determined in the height profile of the image, resulting in a value of 167 ± 101 nm. In the case of the diameter, it was determined in AFM height image, obtaining a value of 5.6 ± 1.5 nm. Thereby, an L/D aspect ratio of 30 was obtained.

Fig. 2. a) Particle size and distribution of WBPUU dispersion, b) and c) images of WBPUU dispersion after the synthesis process and after 6 months, respectively. AFM d) height and e) phase images of isolated CNC (size: $3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^2$).

3.2. Polyurethane-urea films characterization

CNC, WBPUU and nanocomposites characteristic functional groups were analyzed by FTIR and the spectra are shown in Fig. 3a. WBPUU spectra presented two main regions: between 3600 and 3100 cm^{-1} , the peak related with the N-H groups of urethane and urea groups stretching vibration was observed, whereas in the region from 1800 to 1600 cm^{-1} , amide I region, the peak attributable to carbonyl (C=O) groups stretching vibration was appreciated [27]. Furthermore, CNC showed two peaks at 3332 and 3287 cm^{-1} , attributable to the hydroxyl (O-H) groups of CNC [28]. Nanocomposites FTIR spectra showed a progressive increase in the N-H stretching vibration region of the WBPUU, which became sharper with CNC addition due to the overlapping with the O-H groups peak of CNC in that region. In amide I region, displayed in the inset of Fig. 3a, between 1800 and 1600 cm^{-1} , nanocomposites also showed a characteristic band related with the carbonyl groups of PCL, urethane and urea groups which shifted to different wavenumbers depending the nature and interactions ability of C=O groups [29]. It was observed that the addition of CNC promoted that the peak about 1720 cm^{-1} observed in WBPUU shifted to higher wavenumbers, whereas the shoulder at 1700 cm^{-1} was broadened to lower wavenumbers.

Thermal and thermomechanical behavior of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites films was analyzed by DSC and DMA. DSC thermograms are shown in Fig. 3b. Polyurethane-ureas can be considered as block copolymers, presenting different transitions in relation to the soft and hard segments [25,30,31].

Usually transitions at low temperatures are associated to soft segment domains, whereas transitions at higher temperatures are related to hard segment domains [32]. In both cases, soft and hard segments can be arranged in amorphous or ordered domains [33]. In this case, soft segment glass transition temperature, and hard segment melting temperature and enthalpy obtained from thermograms are shown in Table 1. Regarding soft segment, it was observed that in general, CNC addition conferred greater mobility to amorphous soft segment domains, resulting in lower T_{gSS} values [34]. Otherwise, about 70 °C, WBPUU and nanocomposites showed an endothermic transition which can be related with the short range order of the hard segment [35]. With the purpose of analyzing the transition, the relative hard segment crystallinity of nanocomposites (χ_{cHS}) with respect to the neat WBPUU was determined. In this way, it was possible to analyze in more detail HS behavior in each nanocomposite. Thus, χ_{cHS} was calculated by means of the following Equation [36]:

$$\chi_{cHS} = \frac{\Delta H_{mHS}}{\omega \cdot \Delta H_{100}}$$

where ΔH_{100} is referred to the melting enthalpy of the neat WBPUU, ω the weight fraction of WBPUU in the nanocomposite and ΔH_{mHS} the melting enthalpy of the corresponding nanocomposite. It has to be worth noting that CNC addition provided higher T_{mHS} values comparing with the matrix, indicating that CNC acted as nucleating agent [27,37]. At low CNC content (0.5 wt%) it was observed that CNC could act as nucleating points, resulting in higher T_{mHS} and enthalpy, obtaining thus slightly higher relative hard segment crystallinity. At higher CNC content, despite nanocomposites presented higher T_{mHS} values than the matrix, ΔH_{mHS} tended to decrease, which could be attributed to the hindrance generated by the higher ordered domains.

Table 1. Thermal properties of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites.

Sample	T_{gSS} (°C)	T_{mHS} (°C)	ΔH_{mHS} (J g ⁻¹)	χ_{cHS}
WBPUU	-43.7	68.7	6.5	1
WBPUU-0.5	-46.4	71.4	7.0	1.08
WBPUU-1	-45.7	72.1	5.7	0.89
WBPUU-3	-47.1	73.4	6.5	1.03
WBPUU-5	-45.7	72.7	5.8	0.94

Fig. 3. a) FTIR spectra of CNC, matrix and nanocomposites. b) DSC thermograms, c) storage modulus and $Tan\delta$ curves and d) stress-strain curves of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites.

The thermomechanical behavior of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposite films was studied by DMA, analyzing the evolution of storage modulus and $Tan\delta$ with increasing temperature, as is shown in Fig. 3c. It was observed that in the glassy state all samples showed similar E' values, although slightly higher values were reached in the case of high CNC contents (3 and 5 wt%). At higher temperatures, in the range between -50 and -30 °C, a drop in E' curves was observed associated to the T_{gSS} of films. This transition was also reflected as a peak in $Tan\delta$ curves. It was observed that the peak resulted broader and less intense at high CNC contents, where the influence of CNC in the restriction of WBPUU chains mobility would be more notable [38–41]. As temperature was increased, at low CNC contents (0.5 and 1 wt%), lower E' values were observed in both cases comparing with the matrix.

This fact could be ascribed to the low CNC content and the way of interfering in the WBPUU neat interactions. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the thermomechanical stability of WBPUU-1 nanocomposite was slightly enhanced. For nanocomposites loaded with 3 and 5 wt% of CNC, E' curves showed higher values comparing with the matrix, attributed to the effective reinforcement effect of CNC, providing more interactions with the matrix, as observed by FTIR, and conferring higher rigidity to the nanocomposites [42]. Furthermore, the second drop in E' curves referred to melting of the short range order of hard segment domains was significantly retarded denoting the higher thermomechanical stability of nanocomposites conferred by CNC incorporation [43].

Mechanical behavior of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites is shown by stress-strain curves in Fig. 3d. Furthermore, stress at yield, stress at break, tensile modulus and strain at break values of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposite films obtained from the stress-strain curves are summarized in Table 2. It was observed that CNC contributed to the increase of E maintaining σ_y , σ_b and ϵ_b values similar to those of the matrix in the case of nanocomposites loaded up to 3 wt% of CNC. This fact was related

with the effective CNC reinforcement effect [44], resulting in stiffer films. At 5 wt% of CNC content, ϵ_b was considerably reduced due to the restriction of WBPUU chains mobility by CNC addition [34]. Moreover, the percolation threshold in the nanocomposite was estimated theoretically as previously reported in literature [45] and the value was determined at about 3.2 wt%, which is in accordance with the results obtained in those nanocomposites. Cao et al. [44] observed that at higher CNC loading than percolation threshold value, the strain at break decreased considerably, in agreement with the trend observed in this work. Thereby, at the highest CNC content in this work, a percolated CNC network is expected to be formed, which would reduce the strain at break of the nanocomposite.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites.

Sample	σ_y (MPa)	σ_b (MPa)	E (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)
WBPUU	10.6 ± 0.6	16.9 ± 1.5	169.3 ± 5.0	389 ± 20
WBPUU-0.5	10.2 ± 1.1	16.0 ± 1.9	186.9 ± 24.8	377 ± 23
WBPUU-1	11.5 ± 0.6	16.0 ± 1.2	194.5 ± 19.9	334 ± 9
WBPUU-3	11.3 ± 0.8	15.5 ± 1.0	218.8 ± 14.7	333 ± 53
WBPUU-5	13.4 ± 0.3	15.5 ± 0.7	317.4 ± 26.0	189 ± 37

The hydrophilicity of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposite films was analyzed by static water contact angle measurements and water absorption measurements. Concerning contact angle measurements, 90° is the reference value, which differs the hydrophobic ($> 90^\circ$) or hydrophilic ($< 90^\circ$) character of films surface [29]. WBPUU matrix showed a moderate hydrophilic character showing a value around $79.1 \pm 0.7^\circ$. In the case of nanocomposites, although WCA values did not varied significantly, the incorporation of CNC contributed to a slightly more hydrophilic character of the films (78.9 ± 1.4 , 79.9 ± 0.2 , 77.8 ± 0.6 and $76.8 \pm 0.8^\circ$ for WBPUU-0.5, WBPUU-1, WBPUU-3 and WBPUU-5, respectively) [46]. Furthermore, the similar deviation values ($1-2^\circ$) observed in the nanocomposites, suggested the homogeneous surface of films.

In order to analyze the hydrophilic behavior of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites immersed in water, water absorption measurements at 25°C were carried out, and results are shown in Fig. 4. Analyzing the results, in general different behaviors were observed attending to CNC content at low and high water absorption times. In the case of low CNC contents (0.5 wt%), it was observed an analogous to matrix water absorption behavior, showing a similar water absorption curve but greater absorption capacity due to the hydrophilic character of CNC [47]. At higher CNC content, the water absorption behavior changed, where it was appreciated an overshoot in water absorption percentages at low times. In this case, interactions between CNC and water could weaken their bonding with the matrix, allowing the release of swollen CNC to the medium, contributing to the observed weight decrease.

Fig. 4. Water absorption percentages over time of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposite films.

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The morphology of WBPUU and the dispersion of CNC in the nanocomposites were analyzed by AFM. Fig. 5a shows the height and phase images of $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ of nanocomposites. AFM images showed WBPUU matrix morphology, where bright and dark regions were appreciated, related to the hard and soft domains, being indicative of the existence of a microphase separated morphology [48]. Furthermore, it was observed that CNC incorporation hardly varied the morphology of the matrix. In order to discern CNC more accurately, Fig. 5b shows AFM phase images of $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$ of nanocomposites, where the presence of greater quantity of CNC was appreciated as CNC content was increased. Moreover, it is worth noting that CNC showed a suitable dispersion, being homogeneously distributed in the matrix [49]. In this way, AFM images supported the idea that the creation of WBPUU-CNC interactions was facilitated as it was observed in FTIR and DSC results. In addition, as it can be seen in Fig. 5b, CNC seemed to be surrounded by WBPUU, which could be the responsible of the little variation in the hydrophilicity of nanocomposites films surface, reflected in the similar WCA values.

Fig. 5. AFM a) height (left) and phase (right) images of WBPUU matrix and nanocomposites (size: $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$) and b) amplification of phase images (size: $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$).

4. Conclusions

In this work, a WBPUU was synthesized where the diamine chain extension step was performed in homogeneous medium, prior to dispersion formation, leading to small particle sizes with a narrow distribution, which favors the stability over months. Based on the WBPUU dispersion, a series of nanocomposites loaded with different CNC contents (from 0.5 to 5 wt%) were prepared by casting. The morphological analysis by AFM corroborated the effective dispersion of CNC in the matrix, which favored the creation of WBPUU-CNC interactions as observed by FTIR and DSC. Furthermore, thermal analysis revealed that CNC presented the capacity of acting as nucleating agents, providing greater mobility to chains, reflected in lower T_{gSS} comparing with the matrix and increasing T_{mHS} . In addition, an enhancement in the thermomechanical stability was observed, especially in nanocomposites with high CNC content (3 and 5 wt%). In general, the effective CNC incorporation resulted in stiffer films, showing an increase in E and σ_y , maintaining high ϵ_b values, except for the highest CNC content. Regarding hydrophilicity of films, slight differences were appreciated in WCA values, indicating the similar surface hydrophilicity of the nanocomposites. Nevertheless, more meaningful variations were appreciated in water absorption measurements, where the increase in CNC content favored water molecules diffusion process through the film.

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